

ANALYSIS OF THE MEDICINAL PROPERTIES AND COMPOSITION OF THE SHEPHERD'S PURSE PLANT

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Annotation: The medicinal raw material is the ground part of plants: green fruits, stems, flowers. The composition of raw materials includes tannins, carbohydrates, saponins, choline and acetylcholine, vitamins (ascorbic acid, thiamine, carotene, riboflavin, phyloquinone), organic acids (tartaric, malic, citric and fumaric), fatty and allyl mustard oils.

Key words: green fruits, stems, flowers, tannins, proteins, carbohydrates, saponins, choline and acetylcholine, vitamins, ascorbic acid, thiamine, carotene, riboflavin, phyloquinone, organic acids, tartaric, malic, citric and fumaric.

Introduction

Shepherd's purse (lat. Capsella), or handbag - a genus of herbaceous plants of the Cabbage family. The scientific name capsella is translated from Latin as "casket, box", and describes the shape of the fruits of the representatives of the genus. The shepherd's purse plant, or shepherd's purse (lat. Capsella bursa-pastoris) is a medicinal plant, the most common species of the genus in culture. It is a cosmopolitan plant that grows throughout the tropical and temperate zones of the globe. The specific epithet bursa-pastoris literally means "shepherd's bag".

Grass shepherd's purse is an annual plant with a height of 20 to 60 cm with a spindle-shaped thin root. The stem of the plant is erect, solitary, simple or branched, usually glabrous, but sometimes pubescent in the lower part with simple and branched hairs. Petiolate, pinnatipartite, with entire, sharp triangular or serrated lobes, the basal leaves of the plant are collected in a rosette. The upper leaves with an arrow-shaped base are almost linear. The white flowers of the plant are collected in an umbrella-shaped elongated brush. The fruit of the shepherd's purse is a pod with seeds, reaching both in length and in width from 5 to 8 mm(fig-1). Shepherd's purse flowers from April to August and fruits ripen from May to September[1-8].

Fig-1

The shepherd's purse flower is so widespread that it does not require special cultivation, but if you want to use it constantly, then try to collect plant seeds during the summer. Shepherd's purse is sown in early spring: the plant has a rather long growing season, and during summer sowing, the plant will have time to give flower stalks this year, but will not form rosettes. When sown in autumn, seedlings will appear next spring. As soon as the snow melts, find a sunny or semi-shady area in the garden with moist and nutritious soil and prepare it for planting as you prepare the soil for mustard leaf or cabbage. The seeds of the shepherd's handbag are mixed with sand in a ratio of 1:5 and sown on the surface of the site in even rows located at a distance of 20-25 cm from each other. From above, the crops are only lightly sprinkled with earth. The first shoots may appear in 5-10 days. Rules of care Water the shepherd's bag only in a protracted drought. The plant does not require loosening the soil between the rows, but the shepherd's bag is fed once a season with complex mineral fertilizer for flowering plants, although this is not necessary. From time to time it will be necessary to remove large weeds from the site that obscure the plant from the sun. Microscopic examination of the leaves is shown as follows(fig-2).

fig-2

Methods and results

Shepherd's purse is resistant to diseases and pests of cabbage crops, but can suffer from cruciferous flea and powdery mildew. Dusting a shepherd's purse with ash can get rid of a flea, and it is better to fight powdery mildew with folk remedies (mullein, ash infusion, soda ash solution) or biofungicides (Fitosporin-M, Alirin-B, Gamair, Planriz or Pseudobacterin-2).

The medicinal raw material is the ground part of the plant: green fruits, stems, flowers. The composition of raw materials includes tannins, proteins, carbohydrates, saponins, choline and acetylcholine, vitamins (ascorbic acid, thiamine, carotene, riboflavin, phylloquinone), organic acids (tartaric, malic, citric and fumaric), fatty and allyl mustard oils.

In traditional and folk medicine, shepherd's purse is known primarily for its hemostatic effect. It is used for pulmonary bleeding and various kinds of injuries. Shepherd's purse in gynecology is used to stop uterine bleeding after abortion and childbirth, with uterine fibroids, to delay ovulation, and even as a contraceptive. Shepherd's purse herb is included in the blood-purifying herbal preparations used for cystitis, urolithiasis, pyelonephritis to neutralize and remove toxins accumulated in the body due to medication. Shepherd's purse also has a wound-healing, vasodilating, astringent, anti-inflammatory, diuretic, anti-febrile effect.

The discussion of the results

Shepherd's purse tea is prescribed to regulate pressure in weak hearts, especially in the elderly.

Shepherd's purse infusion is effective for problems of the digestive tract, in particular for dysentery, liver diseases, gastritis, stomach and duodenal ulcers. It is used as a cholagogue for vomiting, cholelithiasis and cholecystitis, and its diuretic will be useful for gout, urinary incontinence and rheumatism. Fresh juice from the leaves of the plant is taken orally 40-50 drops for diarrhea and rheumatism, and for bleeding, the juice is dripped into the nose. A decoction of shepherd's purse is used externally for lotions and compresses for bruises, ulcers, tumors and cuts. Shepherd's purse tincture is used in folk medicine to stop pulmonary, gastric and intestinal bleeding, prolonged menstruation and to strengthen the reproductive organs.

Infusion: pour 10 g of dry grass with a glass of boiling water, close, leave for half an hour, strain through 2-3 layers of gauze and take 1 tablespoon 3-4 times a day for internal bleeding 3-4 times a day for half an hour before meals. The course of treatment is 2-3 weeks. Tea: 2 teaspoons of herbs pour a quarter cup of boiling water, leave for 10 minutes, strain and drink 2 cups a day. Water for tea is better to take purified or thawed. Decoction: Pour 2 tablespoons of grass with a glass of boiling water, boil for a minute, remove from heat, cover, leave for half an hour, strain and use for lotions and compresses.

Fresh leaves of a young shepherd's purse are very rich in vitamins, so they can be used to make salads, borscht, soups and as a filling for pies and pies. Contraindications It is strictly forbidden to use shepherd's purse preparations during pregnancy, hemorrhoids, thrombophlebitis, varicose veins and increased blood clotting.

Experimental part

The extraction can be carried out using various methods: maceration, percolation, repercolation, countercurrent extraction, circulation extraction, percolation with a battery of percolators. To extract raw materials in the form of an extractant, ethyl alcohol of various concentrations is used, other extractants with the addition of acids, alkalis, glycerol, chloroform, etc., depending on the physicochemical properties of the active substances. Liquid extracts are concentrated extracts from medicinal plant materials. The content of active ingredients in liquid extracts is equal to their content in the feedstock prepared in a ratio of 1:1. In the production of liquid extracts, percolation and repercolation methods are used. The percolation method for obtaining liquid

extracts is characterized by the following: percolation (at a constant speed) is carried out until 85 parts by volume of the extract are obtained from 100 parts by weight of the raw material. This extract is a finished product - a liquid extract. Then continue the percolation into another receiver until the raw material is completely depleted. The resulting extract is evaporated under vacuum at a temperature of 50-60°C to a thick mass, which is added to the first extract (85 hours) and, if required, an extractant is added to obtain 100 volume parts of a liquid extract. Purification of liquid extracts is carried out in the same way as tinctures - by settling for several days at a temperature of 8-10 ° C, followed by filtration. Standardization is carried out according to indicators: the content of active substances, the content of ethanol, the composition was determined by mass spectrometric methods.

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